

AI and India

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Abstract

Today without artificial intelligence no industries and other service firms can do nothing. It has become an indispensable part perhaps, another factor of production. India have great accessibility for young scientists, engineers, doctors, professionals etc. Fewer are dedicated towards AI research field and innovation. This have resulted inadequate expertise in AI field and thus block India moreover backward in terms of AI innovation. In spite of this, banking sector gaining much importance towards AI adoption. Recently our NDA government initiated national programme or policy on AI in India. Adoption of AI really boosts Indian economy and however leads the world. Presently, India requires another revolution called AI revolution to upgrade its technological innovations and compete in the world market. This research paper stress more on AI and its innovation, development, improvisation in India. India is still backward in AI innovation due to many issues. It is craving for improvement in technological infrastructure in terms of AI adoption so as to meet the speed of China and U.S. Finally, this paper analyzes the future of India in terms of AI that it can really succeed or not.

Keywords; artificial intelligence, India, accessibility, adequate expertise, NDA government, revolution, improvisation.

Introduction

Artificial intelligence is an intelligence which is demonstrated by the machines. It counters human and animal cognitive functions. The main cause for the emergence of artificial intelligence is that technology advancement and our apparent dependence on it. Growth or development moves parallel to AI adoption as well as advancement in any economy. It was started in early eighties but became full-fledged during 90s and 2000 commercially. The main intention behind AI adoption is to solve problems like learning, recognition of speech, planning, knowledge etc. Artificial intelligence includes computer science, mathematics, linguistics, psychology, neuroscience, philosophy etc. Present artificial intelligence has gone up to the extent of automation in all fields like transportation, health, somewhere in education sector and also in military. Today artificial intelligence has become indispensable part of technology industry.

AI and INDIA

India is the land for different languages, different culture and for different masses. Therefore, there is diversity for scripts, dialects and for dress culture. Thus, for AI it is very challenge in India because

of these diversities and becomes very resilient. What W.W. Rostow had advocated in his growth doctrine, is that; five stages for economic growth. Each economy has to go through these five stages that is from traditional society, pre-condition for take-off, take-off, drive to maturity and to age of high mass consumption. It is known fact that all developed economies have already reached the stage of age of high mass consumption, but India is yet to reach in fact it has reached the stage of drive to maturity, which means, there are certain changes taken place in some sectors like for example; unskilled to skilled labor, changes in entrepreneurial activities, industrialization along with new strategy for R&D. Presently, India require a new revolution to attain the stage of high mass of consumption. Henceforth, there is a requirement for new strategy, new innovation, new type of training for skilled workforce perhaps new class to reach the last stage which indicates to be technologically strong and lead other developed economies. Perhaps, India is craving for that type of resolution.

India is striving hard to catch up the speed of China and U.S in terms of AI innovation and implication in field study. It can be said that India needs another revolution. Before it had industrial revolution and made great impact on economic growth and development but now it requires attention of AI and AI revolution, that is to transformation from industrialization to robotization or digitization. When it comes to attention towards AI implication and innovation, India’s attention towards it is less compared to China and US.

China and U.S. are far ahead in adoption of AI technology and also on innovation. China often recognized as land of robotics, in fact, for robotics and other AI innovation China and U.S. is the birth place. This is because of high investment on AI. These two economies, roughly say about 15-20% contributes from GDP. Whereas India it contributes only 0.002-0.005% of its GDP towards AI. For India majority of its GDP is from service sector like BPO companies. Following table reveals the concentration of two developing countries like India and China on research and development (AI).

Particulars	China	India
Absolute R&D	409.2	50.3
Number of researchers	3926	546

Source; UBS research.

This table information is based on recent research handled by UBS, clearly shows low concentration level of AI in India compared to China. India being one of the top country in terms of producing end number of engineers, doctors and etc. There is uncountable institution, private engineering colleges, but the fact is only few would choose research and innovation, remaining would opt for IT. Today in India there are more of start-ups company and at the same time due to industrialization and urbanization many MNCs companies have set up in industrial cities like Bangalore and Hyderabad and so on. There are handful of AI companies in India along with lack of technology infrastructure.

All experts thank federal government for its initiative to explore AI innovation and implication in India. On February 2018 NITI Aayog came up with NATIONAL PROGRAMME ON AI on order to have digitization. The profounder are Narendra Modi, Prime Minister and Arun Jatlee, a center finance minister. This bought festival mood for private sector, technology firm to boost their performance by adopting AI. Prior to NITI Aayog, many technology firms have already adopted AI into their business as mainstream in order to compete with global market. The recommendation of AI by NITI Aayog is to boost six sectors. They are, health care, agriculture, education, finance

sector, smart cities and infrastructure, and smart mobility and transportation. If this succeeds, its off sure that India's GDP would increase to \$6 trillion by 2027. This AI implication programme on different sectors includes robotics, autonomous trucks, advanced financial technology and such.

Opportunities or Strength for AI in India

India, on one hand aiming for better future in terms technology and on the other hand it is increasing productivity in all the sectors through investment process. Some sectors may be exempted like for example agricultural sector. Perhaps it is doing good nowadays with digitalization policy. India on every academic schedule produce large number of engineers, doctors, IT students etc. Around 2020 or 2025 India may called as young country with youth bulge. AI innovation and companies may offer god jobs for this young masses. There is no threat for employment opportunity in India because, today, majority of the industries, firm, enterprise is indulged in AI technics. In private education institution they started adding AI technical course along with major subjects so to young generation can imbibe certain skill regarding research and development. Certainly yes that BPO stay as back office for India's data collection, analyzation and such process. It is statically proved that BPO and IT firms contributes more to India's GDP today. They might find opportunity in data cleaning, classification and tagging. Increase in human population (mobile subscribers) along with skill development may be plus point for development of AI in India. Industrial cities like Bengaluru and Hyderabad are found to be most favor to IT firms due to number of industries, trading and investment funding. Compare to previous statics data, today India's literacy rate is high. This shows that India has educated population and it would be easy to train them. Work force are very elegant and comprehensive about know-how of technology.

Risks

There are many discussion and debate going on that AI would still job. With reference to India, as major contribution to its GDP is from service sector like tech. firms it could adversely affect. In future, AI can make IT service to be fully automated and there would be no chance for work force to be secured in job environment. Apparently, there are few companies who adopted AI. Until and unless AI becomes as a mainstream India cannot progress in this field. First of all, there is low level of funding from the government side. China and U.S. contributes around 20-30% of its GDP for AI innovation and research whereas India still remains in decimal. Funding is very small compared to these countries. It is said that every year India produce huge number of engineers, researcher, mathematicians, staticians and such. But the tragedy is only few is available as expertise, professionals and such. Where majority of them goes for IT. Therefore, there is adequate availability expertise, professionals in order to take up AI research and development. AI requires qualitated and quantitated data. In India there is improper data distribution. Government investment on technological infrastructure and on encouraging new comers can play major role in developing AI in India. The presence of lack of collaboration between different departments, lack of expertise as it is said, lack of creativity power in young masses as they fear for risk taking all these add to the problem for AI in India. India is the country of many languages and many cultures. This pose serious issues in terms of translation of language and some culture might accept or not. Lastly there should be AI fluency in order to have AI innovation and development. In developing nations like India, there is lack of technological fluency. Today India has 58% of industries, but only countable have adopted AI techniques. There is no awareness regarding AI. In developed countries they have already started AI in diploma and other engineering courses in order to bring AI awareness among young experts. Based on IP (intellectual property) index India has ranked 43 out of 45 countries (2017 global IP index). According to 2016 statistics, only 45000 patents

were signed in India whereas China in the same year went up to 1.1 million patents. All these are obstacles to India in order to AI improvement and adoption.

Can India Really Succeed in AI?

There are huge number of engineers, researcher, mathematicians, statistician in India. But they are adequate. In some sector like banking sector AI adoption is doing good job. Moreover, it is inevitable for banking sector to have AI. Private banks have already installed robotics for better customer service and Ai techniques like chatsbot etc. When it comes to industrial and other IT firms, only few have adopted AI. It is glad and some experts are very much happy about the Indian government forming a policy regarding AI during budget summation. Firstly, India has to resolve all those obstacles for AI. For this it requires, upgradation, training, innovation, reskilling workforce, data quality and quantity, proper funding on research and development. It should change from pilot survey to mainstream survey. Widespread of network line or area can overcome some issues. Experts says that AI doesn't solve 90% of problem. It provides some solution to the extent. Therefore, manifestation of AI on core firms or sectors can overcome some issues. AI is like a new factor of production. It completely transforms every sector. Many experts advocate that, no country is doing with social sector. India can take up AI innovations on social sector. Proper investment, funding can make India to move ahead with AI. Lastly upgradation, new form of handling can bring or do wonders in AI field.

A country leads the world only when it leads to the AI innovation and research. Today it is AI world and because of its revolution many economies are developed and developing. India still backward in AI adoption but it is true that in future it will lead the world I all the terms.

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